

TEACHING READING STRATEGIES IN ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15192751>

Abstract

The language learners should have the good reading skills. Some people say that good learners – who are capable in reading. However, making a connection between learners and reading is pretty hard for who are learning English language as a second language (ESL) or foreign language (EFL) and it requires to adapt various reading strategies. This article is about one of the essential foreign language learning skill – reading.

Keywords: reading strategies, aspects, cognitive, metacognitive, social, effective, methods.

Аннотация

Изучающие язык должны иметь хорошие навыки чтения. Некоторые говорят, что хорошие ученики – те, кто способен читать. Однако установление связи между учениками и чтением довольно сложно для тех, кто изучает английский язык как второй язык (ESL) или иностранный язык (EFL), и это требует адаптации различных стратегий чтения. Эта статья об одном из основных навыков изучения иностранного языка – чтении.

Ключевые слова: стратегии чтения, аспекты, когнитивные, мета когнитивные, социальные, эффективные, методы.

Introduction.

English is using as an international connection means nowadays. This language learners' main purpose is to learn four main skills – reading, writing, listening and speaking. The most crucial part of learning a foreign language is reading. It is main source in both Uzbek, English, and in any language. Children get most of the knowledge from reading in schools, so teaching this skill at an early age would be great. English as a foreign language plays an important role in social, economic, and scientific progress. Khan (2007) said, English is the main source of communication around the world. Muhammad (2013) said that English is taught as a second or foreign language in many countries

The main aspects of language - listening, speaking, reading and writing – was considered very important by some researchers. Reading, is the link between learner and text, is the ability that learning consciously and adopting

suitable strategies for reading (Anderson 2003). Grabe (1991) considered reading is key aspect to understand academic contexts. So researchers think that realizing and reading strategies are essential whether in first or second language. Unless the learners aware of these strategies, they cannot get any benefits, also they do tasks wrongly, not get better results and even lose their motivation

Challenges in teaching reading.

Although the importance of reading was emphasized, it is still a major problem that learners face. Usually students do not have any will to study reading, but it is compulsory and they need to get higher marks. We should give more attention to reading. Teaching foreign language should be free and students should attend with their inspiration. Anderson (1999) the intention of fully understanding the text mostly leads to translate every meaning of the word, as a result it could slow the process of learning. However, studies show that, the interest of student to reading is quite low. In 2008, NEA (National Endowment for the Art) did a research with college students in the USA and the result: in 1982 the rate of reading habits was 59.8 % whereas in 2008 was 51.7 %. Even though reading is important, students think it is boring or complex.

Good learners – who have the ability in good reading skills. They use various kind of strategies and they can apply these strategies in different tasks. Anderson (1999) said, reading strategies – actions are done consciously and constructively by learners. With the help of reading strategies learners can understand better the meaning of the text, learn more vocabularies, find the main ideas and give their opinions freely. When foreign language learners realize the core of the strategies and use them, their approach to study will enhance significantly. At first the main focus on knowing the words and phrases, after using strategies students concentrate on finding overall meaning of the text, understanding the main ideas and analyzing the text. Mostly, teachers use traditional and grammar methods, but target language is used less only.

Studies in that field.

Using reading strategies are so helpful to second language learning students. Oxford divided the strategies to this groups:

Cognitive – gathering important ideas;

Metacognitive – planning and controlling academic performance;

Social – conversation with others;

Effective – inspiring and motivating to study.

Carrell (1998) discovered that using strategies can increase the rate of understanding the text. Barnett (1988) found that applying advanced strategies shows students can understand better the meaning.

Grabe (2009) suggested that teachers should more attention to students in order to adopt efficiently these strategies. Most of the studies (Pressley & Afflerbach, 1995; Zhang, 2001) shows that teachers could change the students' perspective to study by teaching the strategies. Molla (2015) mentioned the importance of the social strategies, even cognitive and metacognitive strategies are important in reading process, he thought social strategies are essential as them. As to him, social strategies – is the way of establishing social collaboration with working others for overcoming study obstacles and achieving success. Reading can enhance spelling and enrich students' vocabulary (Carson, 2000; Kolawole, 2009), and it can improve literacy rate that is essential for various context conversations. So many researches are dedicated to the role and importance of reading (for instance, Chege, 2012; Grim, 2008; Keskin, 2013; Koda, 2007; Snow, 2002) and they showed that students who are effective readers and use reading strategies achieve more academic success and become knowledgeable.

Most of the researches were held to know that the teachers used reading strategies how effects on the students' English language reading results. According to that Khezrlou (2012) investigated, he found a connection between reading strategies and students' results. Applying and effects of these strategies can differentiate between various age groups and level of education.

Conclusion.

According to the above mentioned definitions and researches we can conclude that reading strategies – the process of using intelligence quotient to understand the text and solve problems. It includes understanding general meaning, getting the right information form long parts, increasing self-realization, and predicting the future tasks.

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